

Thermodynamic Functions of Ionisation of Benzoic and Substituted Benzoic Acids in Water and Formamide : Additive Substituent Effects

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Thermodynamic ionisation constants (${}^T pK_a^m$) of benzoic, 3-nitrobenzoic, 3,5-dinitrobenzoic, 3-chlorobenzoic, 3,5-dichlorobenzoic, 3-hydroxybenzoic, 3,5-dihydroxybenzoic, 3-methylbenzoic and 3,5-dimethylbenzoic acids have been determined in water and formamide by employing electromotive force measurements of buffer cells in the temperature range 5–45°. Values of standard free energy (ΔG°), enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°) changes associated with their ionisation are also calculated. Additivity of substituent effects for the ionisation of 3,5-disubstituted benzoic acids in both water and formamide have been discussed. The results indicate that the ionisation process is relatively insensitive to steric effects.

In earlier communications¹⁻³, we reported the thermodynamic ionisation constants of benzoic and monosubstituted (e.g. in *ortho*-, *meta*- or *para*-position) nitro-, chloro-, bromo-, iodo-, hydroxy-, methyl-, methoxy- and aminobenzoic acids in formamide, ethanol, ethylene glycol, propylene glycol and tetrahydrofuran, and in various mixed solvents, and discussed the substituent effects in the *meta*-position of a benzene ring in the respective solvents. But, no work seems to have been done on the substituent effects from the two *meta*-positions of a benzene ring with relation to the proton ionisation of a *meta*-substituted benzoic acids in water as well as in non-aqueous solvents. However, similar studies have been made on the *meta*-substituted phenols and anilinium ions in aqueous medium⁴. We now report the thermodynamic functions of ionisation for 3,5-dinitro-, 3,5-dichloro-, 3,5-dihydroxy- and 3,5-dimethylbenzoic acids in water and formamide at different temperatures ranging from 5 to 45° from electromotive force measurements of buffer cells of the type : Ag(s), AgCl(s) | MCl(m_3), MA(m_2), HA(m_1), QH₂-Q | pt, where M is K or Na, and HA is the disubstituted benzoic acid.

Calculations : The ionisation constant (K_a^m) is given by equation (1),

$$K_a^m = \left(m_{H^+} m_{A^-} / m_{HA} \right) \left(\gamma_{H^+} \gamma_{A^-} / \gamma_{HA} \right) \\ = \left(m_{H^+} m_{A^-} / m_{HA} \right) \gamma_{\pm} \quad (1)$$

where m and γ are the molalities and activity coefficients of the species respectively (assuming $\gamma_{H^+} = \gamma_{A^-} = \gamma_{\pm}$, and $\gamma_{HA} = 1$). The apparent hydrogen ion molality, m'_{H^+} is related to the e.m.f. (E) of the cell through the relation,

$$-\log m'_{H^+} = \frac{[E - E^\circ(\text{Ag} - \text{AgCl}) + E^\circ(\text{QH}_2 - \text{Q})] F}{2.3026 RT} \\ + \log m_{Cl^-} + 2 \log \gamma_{\pm} = \frac{(E^\circ - E) F}{2.3026 RT} \\ + \log m_3 - \frac{2A \sqrt{I d_0}}{1 + a^2 B \sqrt{I d_0}} \quad (2)$$

where A and B are the Debye-Hückel constants, d_0 is the density of the solvent, m_{Cl^-} the molality of chloride ion, and is taken as equal to m_3 , I the ionic strength of the solution. As a first approximation, I was taken to be equal to $m_2 + m_3$, but subsequently an accurate value was obtained by successive approximation and refinement to a constant value of I , given by

$$I = m_2 + m_3 + m'_{H^+} \quad (3)$$

The apparent ionisation constant ($K_a^{m'}$) was calculated from the expression,

$$\log K_a^{m'} = -\frac{2A \sqrt{I d_0}}{1 + a^2 B \sqrt{I d_0}} + \log \frac{m'_{H^+} (m_2 + m'_{H^+})}{(m_1 - m'_{H^+})} \quad (4)$$

The true (thermodynamic) ionisation constant (${}^T pK_a^m$) was determined from the intercept of the $\log K_a^m$ vs I plot. At each temperature about 7 to 9 readings were taken with m_1 in the range $0.3-0.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$, m_2 in the range $0.2-1.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$ and m_3 in the range $15-80 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$, and I in the range $2-9 \times 10^{-2}$. The final results are tabulated for four disubstituted benzoic acids in water and formamide at different temperatures along with their standard deviations obtained from least-squares method.

In the calculation, the standard electrode potentials of the silver-silver chloride (E° (Ag-AgCl)) and of the quinhydrone (E° (QH₂-Q)) electrodes at

and the value of a° was taken for which the pK_a^m had the least standard deviation. Since the a° parameter is almost insensitive to temperature¹⁴, we therefore sought a single value of a° which would minimise the standard deviations for the whole body of data over the temperature range of 5–45°. The value of a° meeting this requirement was that ascertained from the data at 25°. The values of a° for different acids in water and formamide are shown in Table 1 along with their pK_a^m values.

The standard thermodynamic functions (ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS°) were calculated employing usual temperature coefficient method for water⁷ and formamide¹⁵.

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMIC IONISATION CONSTANTS (${}^T pK_a^m$) OF DISUBSTITUTED BENZOIC ACIDS IN WATER AND FORMAMIDE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Benzoic acid	Temp. (°C)									a Å
	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	
Water										
3,5-Dinitro-	—	—	2.78 ^a	2.77 ^b	2.75 ^b	2.73 ^c	2.70 ^a	2.69 ^d	2.68 ^a	5.0
3,5-Dichloro-	—	—	3.14 ^a	3.12 ^c	3.11 ^b	3.10 ^e	3.08 ^f	3.07 ^c	3.07 ^c	5.5
3,5-Dihydroxy-	—	—	4.05 ^e	4.03 ^f	3.99 ^a	3.96 ^d	3.95 ^d	3.96 ^e	3.94 ^a	5.0
3,5-Dimethyl-	—	—	4.30 ^d	4.28 ^e	4.27 ^a	4.26 ^b	4.24 ^c	4.21 ^b	4.19 ^b	5.5
Formamide										
3,5-Dinitro-	5.08 ^a	4.99 ^b	4.91 ^d	4.82 ^e	4.45 ^c	4.67 ^c	4.60 ^e	4.53 ^f	4.46 ^a	5.5
3,5-Dichloro-	6.09 ^b	6.10 ^b	6.13 ^c	6.11 ^d	6.08 ^d	6.07 ^d	6.09 ^e	6.10 ^f	6.06 ^a	6.0
3,5-Dihydroxy-	6.65 ^c	6.59 ^c	6.53 ^f	6.48 ^d	6.40 ^d	6.37 ^f	6.32 ^c	6.27 ^d	6.22 ^a	6.0
3,5-Dimethyl-	6.62 ^a	6.63 ^c	6.56 ^d	6.50 ^f	6.48 ^e	6.42 ^b	6.44 ^b	6.47 ^c	6.48 ^d	6.0

^a±0.04, ^b±0.06, ^c±0.02, ^d±0.03, ^e±0.05, ^f±0.01.

different temperatures have been taken from literature in formamide⁵ and water¹⁰. The Debye-Hückel constants, A and B for water at different temperatures were taken from the literature^{6a,7} and for formamide calculated using the dielectric constant⁸ in the appropriate equation⁹. The values of d_0 at different temperatures for the solvents were taken from the literature^{10,11}. This calculation requires a suitable choice of the ion-size parameter (a°) and it is well known that a wrong choice of the value of a° is often a source of considerable uncertainty in $pK_a^{12,13}$. To ascertain the correct value of a° , the pK_a^m at 25° was calculated for various values of a° (3 to 6 Å at intervals of 0.5 Å) from the data at that temperature

Results and Discussion

It is of interest to study the additive substituent effects for the proton ionisation of the 3,5-disubstituted benzoic acids in water and formamide. Considering the substituent changes of the type,

where \dot{X} is the substituent and DX is the disubstituted, perfect additivity in ${}^T pK_a^m$ would give δpK_1

equal to δpK_2 . Since the polar effects are almost invariably additive while steric effects are not, such additivity could be taken as an indication that there is no steric interaction between the X substituent and the reaction centre, or between the two X substituents (in 3,5-disubstituted benzoic acids).

If, $\delta pK_1 = \delta pK_2$,

i.e. $T_pK_a^X - T_pK_a^0 = T_pK_a^{DX} - T_pK_a^X$,

then, $T_pK_a^{DX} = 2 T_pK_a^X - T_pK_a^0$ (5)

formamide (correlation coefficient, 0.99999) is observed, having the slope values of 1.9798 ± 0.0013 in water and 1.9897 ± 0.0001 in formamide, and the intercepts of -4.206 ± 0.004 in water (the $T_pK_a^m$ of unsubstituted benzoic acid at 25° is 4.29 in water) and -6.295 ± 0.001 in formamide (the $T_pK_a^m$ of unsubstituted benzoic acid at 25° is 6.36 in formamide).

Standard thermodynamic functions of ionisation are also shown in Table 2 for the acids in water and formamide at 25° . As observed, for the *meta*-substituted benzoic acids, substituent effects on the free energies of ionisation are precisely additive.

TABLE 2—STANDARD FREE ENERGY, ENTHALPY AND ENTROPY CHANGES FOR IONISATION OF BENZOIC AND SUBSTITUTED BENZOIC ACIDS IN WATER (a) AND FORMAMIDE (b) AT 25°

Benzoic acid	$T_pK_a^m$		ΔG° (KJ mol ⁻¹)		ΔH° (KJ mol ⁻¹)		ΔS° (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	
	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)
Benzoic	4.29	6.36	24.48	26.29	0.42	28.92	80.07	27.74
3-Nitro-	3.51	5.40	19.93	30.81	1.34	27.56	62.38	10.91
3,5-Dinitro-	2.75	4.45	15.69	25.39	2.26	26.20	45.07	-2.72
3-Chloro-	3.70	6.22	21.24	35.46	0.08	20.65	71.00	49.71
3,5-Dichloro-	3.11	6.08	17.74	34.69	-0.26	12.42	60.40	74.73
3-Hydroxy-	4.14	6.38	23.58	36.38	16.43	25.69	23.98	35.87
3,5-Dihydroxy-	3.99	6.40	22.76	36.52	32.38	18.37	-32.28	61.28
3-Methyl-	4.28	6.42	24.42	36.63	0.29	18.37	80.96	61.28
3,5-Dimethyl-	4.27	6.48	24.36	36.97	0.12	7.90	81.70	97.55

The $T_pK_a^m$ values of the 3,5-dinitro-, 3,5-dichloro-, 3,5-dihydroxy- and 3,5-dimethylbenzoic acids are reproduced in Table 2 along with that of benzoic and the corresponding 3-substituted benzoic acids in water¹⁶ and formamide^{1,17} at 25° .

As observed, the $T_pK_a^m$ values of the 3,5-disubstituted benzoic acids agree well with equation (5) in both water and formamide lending support to the fact that the substituent effects from the two *meta*-positions of a benzene ring on the proton ionisation are precisely additive. From equation (5), it is clear that when the $T_pK_a^m$ values of the 3,5-disubstituted benzoic acids are plotted against the $T_pK_a^m$ values of the equivalent 3-substituted acids, a linear plot with a slope of 2 and an intercept equals to $-T_pK_a^m$ of the unsubstituted acid indicates perfect additivity. Fig. 1 shows such a plot for the $T_pK_a^m$ values of the disubstituted benzoic acids in water and formamide. Excellent linearity in water (correlation coefficient, 0.99999) as well as in

Fig. 1. Plots for the $T_pK_a^m$ values of the mono- and di-substituted benzoic acids in water and formamide at 25° .

Plots of the entropies of ionisation for the 3,5-disubstituted benzoic acids give a high degree of linearity (correlation coefficient, 0.99881, a slope of 1.9897 ± 0.0085 and an intercept of 79.78 ± 0.28 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ (ΔS° of benzoic acid is -80.07 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹)) in water, and in formamide (correlation coefficient, 0.9993, a slope of 1.9559 ± 0.1031 and an intercept of 19.44 ± 2.15 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ (ΔS° of benzoic acid is -27.74 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹)). Allowing for the inevitably large errors of the entropy values, it is apparent that they are just as additive as the $T_p K_a^m$ values.

It seems clear from the results that the substituents do not sterically interact with the reaction centre when in the 3-position of a benzene ring. Their substituent effects from this position are, therefore, presumably purely polar in origin, and whether they are transmitted to the reaction centre through the aromatic ring, through the solvent medium, or through a combination of these two, the effects from the two *meta*-positions are quite additive.

Experimental

Formamide (B D H, L R) was purified as described elsewhere.¹⁸ 3,5-Disubstituted benzoic acids (A R or G R grade) used Potassium or sodium salts of disubstituted benzoic acids were prepared by following the method described earlier.¹ Potassium or sodium chloride (E Merck, G R) was used. The salts were dried at 110–120°. The acids and the salts were stored in vacuum desiccator over anhydrous calcium chloride until required. Quinhydrone was of A R grade. Solutions for e m f measurements were prepared by dissolving the appropriate amounts of acids and salts in known amounts of formamide and conductivity water.

The cell vessels for the buffer cells were of the type recommended by Harned and Wright.¹⁹ The silver-silver chloride electrode was prepared by the method described elsewhere.²⁰ Quinhydrone electrodes were prepared according to the method of Janz and Ives.²¹ Electromotive force measurements were made with a Bajaj (India) potentiometer in conjunction with a d c galvanometer (OSAW) and a Weston standard cell (Muirhead and Co, England).

Procedure For the buffer cell, the silver-silver chloride electrode was placed in the appropriate cell compartment of a clean and dry cell, and filled with cell solution (i.e. solution containing solvent, e.g. formamide or water, salts and acid). The saturated solution of quinhydrone-cell solution was prepared by shaking the cell solution with quinhydrone in a well stoppered bottle for a few minutes in a bath at 0° and then transferred to the quinhydrone compartment of the cell in which the platinised platinum electrode had been previously placed under a dry nitrogen atmosphere. After filling, the cell was kept in the thermostat maintained at the required temperature (accurate $\pm 0.1^\circ$).

The e m f of the cell with formamide solution was found to decrease slowly with time with a varying rate, possibly due to the slow thermal decomposition of formamide²⁰, whereas the e m f of the cell containing aqueous solution remained practically constant with time. E m f readings were taken at 30 min intervals upto 4–5 h. Extrapolation of these values to zero time (in the case of cell containing formamide solution) was taken as the true e m f of the cell corresponding to zero decomposition of the solvent, formamide²⁰. The reproducibility of the results of the e m f measurements was of the order of ± 0.1 mV.

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